

A Conceptual Study of Green Financing in Promoting Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT

Green financing has been termed as a financial innovative tool that includes a wide range of financial products as well as services to promote sustainability. It particularly specifies social, environmental and government concerns. Sustainable development lays emphasis on the present needs without compromising about the future requirements. The present study aims to focus on understanding the concept of green financing as well as green financing instruments. It also aims to assess the importance of green financing in promoting sustainable development. The data has been collected from secondary sources including journals, articles, internet websites and published reports. Financial instruments basically includes green bonds, green banks, green investment funds that are majorly concerned in lessening pollution or greenhouse gas emissions and simultaneously concerned in improving the economy. Green financing has also been considered as an effective tool in promoting sustainable development as it focuses on maximisation of stakeholder's value creation as well as environment sustainability itself has counted in supporting renewable energy sources.

Keywords: Green Financing, Sustainable Development, Financial Instruments, Environmental Concern

1. Introduction

Green finance has been considered as an important concept of financing in the modern era. It can be seen that in 1992, Green Finance was initiated by United Nations Environment Program Finance Initiative (UNEPFI) with other commercial banks that had jointly promoted environmental concern with banking industry. It includes variety of financial products as well as services including green bonds, green investment funds, climate risk insurance that are classified into banking, insurance and investment related products. It has been created to improve environmental outcome. Variety of environmental objectives are laid including water sanitation, biodiversity protection and controlling industrial pollution. Green financing is also known as responsible investing as it lays emphasis on environmental, social and government concerns. According to Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Green Finance has been defined as finance for “achieving economic growth thereby reducing pollution as well as greenhouse gas emissions and also minimising waste and improving efficiency in the use of natural resources.” Green financing is a term that comprises of sustainable development projects as well as initiatives that use environmentally friendly products and policies that stimulate more sustainable economy (Islam, et al. (2014).

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Green finance as identified by UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also includes the sustainable development criteria that maintain transparency as well as consider long term thinking of investments into environmental objectives.

Green finance includes financial products as well as services that can be further segregated into investment, banking and insurance products. Debt as well as equity is most prominent financial instrument of green finance. Renewable energy investments, sustainable infrastructure finance as well as green bonds continue to be most significant areas within green financing activities.

According to UNESCO, “Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has been considered to encourage the learners through knowledge, skills, values as well as attitudes in taking informed decisions and also in making responsible actions for environment integrity, economic viability and society.” Sustainable Development refers to focusing upon the present needs of environmental development, without concerning about future. It has been considered as a significant economic approach in meeting the present needs of the country and it is basically concerned with social, environment, culture as well as economy.

2. Objectives of the Study

- 2.1 To understand the concept of green financing.
- 2.2 To know the importance of green financing in promoting sustainable development.

3. Methodology of the Study

The present study is mainly based on secondary source of data to get more familiarity about the concept of green financing. Therefore, the data has been taken from various reputed journals, published reports, articles and internet websites that have supported in collecting the required information subject to the acceptance of research objectives as mentioned in the present study.

4. Review of Literature

Islam, Yousuf et al. (2014) aimed to take initiative on optimizing green financing in banking and non-banking financial institutions throughout the economy in Bangladesh. It observed major challenges of green banking practices in Bangladesh including environmental parameters as well as in formulating policies. Moreover, it recommended improving green banking practice including online financing/banking and separate green financing. Furthermore, it concluded that financial industries were considered to be efficient for sustainable development. **Hoshen, Hasan et al. (2017)** aimed to understand the allocation into various green projects of green financing into banking as well as non-banking sectors in Bangladesh. It was observed that contribution by private commercial banks have been progressing day by day into the green projects. Furthermore, it concluded that green funding is essential for eco-friendly projects in promoting sustainable development and in reducing the risk. **Stojanovic and Ilic (2018)** attempted to focus on developing market mechanisms as well as in formulating policies related to green financing. It concluded that it is significant to transform the world economies by implementing the agreement of climate change on global level. Furthermore, it also concluded that the bond market, banking, risk analysis, institutional investors were included in green finance, including sustainable economic

development. **Dörry and Schulz (2018)** aimed to evaluate the link between the finance industry as well as local businesses in adapting sustainable economic practices. It analysed that green financing and economic initiatives in Luxembourg indicated progress in attaining sustainable objectives. It concluded that the traditional approaches to the finance industry as well as specific needs of alternative economic endeavours remains disrupted, however green undertakings were considered well. **Yoshino, Schloesser et al. (2020)** aimed to magnify the overall structure of Home Town Investment Trust (HIT) funds by employing security, auditability, transparency of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) by reducing risk related to investment in HIT fund. It concluded that the application of DLTs were significant in improving finance scheme by tackling real life issues related to currency feature. Furthermore, it was suggested to explore such more potentials on DLTs to spread positive impact on society. **Taghizadeh-Hesary and Yoshino (2020)** aimed to highlight various challenges related to green financing as well as investment in projects related to renewable energy. It attempted to reduce credit risk by introducing public financial institutions as well as non-banking financial institutions through filling green financing gap in long term green investments. It concluded that low rate of return, lack of long-term financing and lack of capacity was considered as significant challenges in developing green projects. Moreover, spillover effects were known to expand the rate of return on green energy projects. **Ng, Nathwani et al. (2021)** aimed to understand the disclosure of green financing system with international capital markets and in fostering energy sustainability of Industry 4.0 by developing globally and in adopting developing economies under green recovery structure. Also, in the advancement of clean energy technologies in making better financial decisions. The study revealed assembling of green financing institutions for turning investments into sustainable infrastructure in reducing climate change in Paris Agreement. **Liu, Yao et al. (2021)** aimed to find that green financing as a highly supporting innovative financing technique. It revealed through findings that GDP had major impact on carbon intensity of trade openness. Moreover, the global economic integration has promoted international economic cooperation. Further, it was suggested for the policymakers in developing energy system friendly policies in granting green finance to energy systems of E7 economies. **Xueying, Sadiq et al. (2021)** aimed to foster the gross domestic product in long run dynamics of E7 and G7 countries. It revealed that GDP of G7 countries was more affected in case of climate change indicators as compared to E7 countries. It concluded that green financing techniques were considered helpful in upgrading the economic growth of G7 and E7 countries through formulation of policies and by cleaning the environment. Furthermore, it was also suggested to change green finance as well as environment conditions from 2010 to 2018 in G-7 and E-7 countries. **Nawaz et al. (2021)** attempted to analyse the climate change mitigation as well as green financing from 2005 to 2019 of N-11 countries and BRIC countries and also evaluated to understand, if any, differences persist in commitments of green financing and strategies of climate change. It suggested to formulate the policies to reduce systematic risks through financing technique for N-11 and BRICS countries. Furthermore, it also recommended that the government should initiate some regulations for developing bond market and green bonds must be introduced to ensure transparency. **Taghizadeh-Hesary et al. (2021)** aimed to analyze the green bond's market performance in Asia and Pacific regions. It revealed that green bonds, specifically in Asia, dominated by the

banking sector had exhibited higher returns with higher risks and higher heterogeneity at the similar side. It observed that traditional banking was not a right source for funding green bonds. It was also suggested for the policy makers to introduce green credit rating sustainability in measuring the green based projects, in bringing down the direct as well as indirect subsidies to fossil fuels as well as in using tax spillover to expand the rate of return of green bonds through finance and banking. **Sheng et al. (2021)** aimed to focus on preferring green bond premium in China by investors through achieving sustainable finance. It emphasized on the issue related to difference between matched conventional bond and green bond. It also indicated that a favourable resourcing environment is possible only through financial institutions rather than the corporate groups. It helped to understand through findings about the issuer's motivation as well as investors' preference for green based projects. Furthermore, it was suggested to adequately optimize the market funds through policies postulated by government or third party verification to the real enterprises.

5. Taxonomy of Green Finance

Green finance is the financing of investment in all financial sectors and asset classes that integrate environmental, social and governance (ESG) criteria into the investment decisions and embed sustainability into risk management for encouraging the development of a more sustainable economy. As ESG reporting shifts from niche to mainstream and begins to have balance sheet implications, investors are raising challenging questions on how ESG performance is assessed, managed, and reported. Indeed, ESG factors are critical in the assessment of the risks to insurer's assets and liabilities, which are threefold: physical risk, transition risk and liability risk. For banks, ESG risks exert an influence on banks' creditworthiness. Banks can then provide sustainable lending in incorporating environmental outcomes in risk and pricing assessments. Institutional investors can incorporate ESG factors in portfolio selection and management to identify risks and opportunities.

Most importantly, a harmonized definition of "green" and taxonomy of green activities are needed to help investors and financial institutions efficiently allocate capital and make well-informed decisions. The definition of green finance needs to be more transparent to prevent "green washing". And a common set of minimum standards on green finance is essential to redirect capital flows towards green and sustainable investments as well as for market and risk analysis and benchmark. Standards and rules for disclosure would help developing green finance assets. Voluntary principles and guidelines for green finance, complemented with regulatory incentives, need to be implemented and monitored for all asset classes.

5.1 Green Finance Market

According to Climate Policy Initiative's Updated view on the Global Landscape of Climate Finance 2019, climate finance flows reached a record high of USD 608 billion in 2017, driven particularly by renewable energy capacity additions in China, the U.S., and India, as well as increased public commitments to land use and energy efficiency. This was followed by 11% drop in 2018 to USD 540 billion. Based on available information, Climate Policy Initiative's initial estimate suggests 2019 climate finance flows will amount to USD 608 – 622 billion, representing a 6% - 8% increase from 2017-18 averages.

Figure 1: Global Landscape of Green Finance Market (in US\$ billion)

Source: International Development Finance club report 2019 (IDFC)

5.2 Multilateral Development Banks:

MDBs have deep institutional expertise in providing and catalyzing investments in sustainable development and taking steps to align their activities with the 2030 Agenda. In 2019, climate financing by the world’s largest MDBs accounted for US\$ 61,562 million, with US\$ 41,467 million or 67 per cent of total MDB commitments for low-income and middle-income economies and US\$ 20,095 million or 33 per cent for high-income economies

Figure 2: MDB’s climate finance commitment 2015-2019 (in US\$ billion)

Source: International Development Finance club report 2019 (IDFC)

5.3 Climate Bonds:

The analysis of annual green bond and loan issuance that meets internationally accepted definitions of green is estimated to be US\$350 bn in 2020, with a 31.8 per cent increase from 2019. At the end of October 2020, the yearly global green bond and loans market reached US\$194.6bn, a 9% increase on the equivalent period in 2019.

Figure 3: Records levels of Climate Bonds at the end of 2021

Source: Sustainable Debt Market Summary 2021 report

Key Highlights:

- ❖ Combined labelled issuance of Green, Social, and Sustainability, Transition, and Sustainability-linked reached **USD 767.5 bn** in the first three quarters of 2021
- ❖ September – largest issuing month ever, **USD 130.6 bn** of total labelled issuance
- ❖ Green bonds reach USD 354.2 bn at end Q3 2021, surpassing 2020 total and now likely to reach half a trillion by year end
- ❖ Trillion in annual green bond issuance within reach for 2023
- ❖ Sustainability-linked bonds reach USD 78.7 bn this year; transition finance reaches USD 5 bn this year

5.4 Green Bond Issuance Highlights

In the primary portion of this current year, Issuance of green obligation instruments kept on filling in the main portion of 2021, with volumes remembered for the Climate Bonds' Green Bond Database¹⁴ in this period dramatically increasing to USD 227.8 bn contrasted with green issuance arrived at what might be compared to more than 3/4 (76%) of entire year 2020 volume. This development rate carries aggregate green security volume to USD 1.3 tn. Our examination proposes that even with a generally unassuming development rate, the yearly issuance volume of green securities could cross USD 1 trillion by 2023.

Figure 4: Annual Trillion in Green Bonds Within Reach by 2023

Source: Sustainable Debt Market Summary 2021 report

6. Green Financing: Social and Sustainability issuance highlights

Whereas green bonds are classified in agreement with the Climate Bonds Taxonomy, social and sustainability bonds raise finances for systems with broader positive impacts across the dimensions of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and beyond specifically climate-related objects. In future, Climate Bonds will seek to integrate a comprehensive social taxonomy – likely acclimatise from work afoot via the International Platform for Sustainable Finance – to enable further robust webbing and assessment of social and sustainability debt instruments.

Table 1: Top 10 Social and Sustainability Issuers in 2021

Label Theme	Name	Country	Amt issued 2021 (USD equivalent)
1. Social	European Union	Supranational	56.1 Bn
2. Social	Caisse d'Amortissement de la Dette Sociale	France	36.8 Bn
3. Social	UNEDIC ASSEO	France	9.7 Bn
4. Sustainability	World Bank (IBRD)	Supranational	7.7 Bn
5. Social and Sustainability	Government of Chile	Chile	6.2 Bn (3.2 Bn Social; 3.0 Bn Sustainability)
6. Sustainability	State of North Rhine-Westphalia Germany	Germany	4.3 Bn
7. Sustainability	Toyota Motor Corp	Japan	4.0 Bn
8. Sustainability	Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank	Supranational	3.9 Bn
9. Sustainability	BNG Bank	Netherlands	2.6 Bn
10. Sustainability	Islamic Development Bank	Supranational	2.5 Bn

Source: Sustainable Debt Market Summary 2021 report

According to UN environment programme, many countries including financial regulators as well as finance sector have joined together in aligning financial systems to the 2030 sustainable development agenda in directing the financial flows. It has been currently working on green financing project to assist public sector in enabling environment, in promoting public and private partnerships on financial products and building capacity for common enterprises on micro-credit. Moreover, environment sustainability has been

considered vital in supporting renewable energy resources through investing in green projects globally. [UNEP, (2018)]

7. Conclusion

Due to unprecedented COVID crisis, the economy of India is also struggling hard to reduce its impact and factors like heat waves, storms and increasing floods have reduced GDP through five percent loss. Green finance investments have been significant in reducing the climate change risk through low carbon emission transport, clean power. Green finance is comprised of green bonds, carbon market instruments and green financial institutions with green banks and green funds. It can also be concluded that green financing is an effective tool in promoting sustainable development while managing risk through direct investment. Green investments are also prioritized while maximizing stakeholder's value creation. Economic and environment benefits can be managed through green financing by ensuring low carbon emission in society. A green multiplier effect is created by investing money into green based projects that significantly help in stimulating the economy as well as in reducing carbon emissions.

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